

Supplementary Table. Multiple infections by tick-borne pathogens according to age classes and overall number of animals.

Ac = *Anaplasma centrale*; *Am* = *Anaplasma marginale*; *Ap* = *Anaplasma platys*; *AspO* = *Anaplasma* sp. Omatjenne; *Er* = *Ehrlichia ruminantium*; *R* = *Rickettsia* spp. (*Rickettsia massiliae* according to 16S rDNA sequencing); *Bb* = *Babesia bigemina*; *Bbov* = *Babesia bovis*; *Tm* = *Theileria mutans*; *Tt* = *Theileria taurotragi*; *Tv* = *Theileria velifera*.

	Tick-borne pathogen species combinations	Number of detections			Totals
		Calves	Juveniles	Adults	
1	<i>Tm_Tt_Tv</i>	1	13	65	79
2	<i>Am_AspO_Tm_Tt_Tv</i>	1	14	27	42
3	<i>Tm_Tv</i>	-	8	26	34
4	<i>Am_AspO</i>	-	4	29	33
5	<i>Am_Tm_Tt_Tv</i>	-	9	18	27
6	<i>Am_AspO_Tm_Tv</i>	-	6	15	21
7	<i>Ap_Tm_Tt_Tv</i>	-	2	10	12
8	<i>Am_AspO_Tm_Tt_Tv_Bb</i>	-	5	7	12
9	<i>Am_Tm_Tv</i>	-	2	9	11
10	<i>Am_AspO_Tm</i>	-	7	3	10
11	<i>Am_Ac_AspO_Tm_Tt_Tv</i>	-	1	9	10
12	<i>AspO_Tm_Tt_Tv</i>	-	-	10	10
13	<i>Am_Ac</i>	1	1	6	8
14	<i>AspO_Tm_Tv</i>	-	1	7	8
15	<i>Tm_Tt_Tv_Bb</i>	-	4	4	8
16	<i>Ap_Tm_Tv</i>	-	-	7	7
17	<i>Am_Tm</i>	1	1	5	7
18	<i>Am_Ac_AspO</i>	-	2	5	7
19	<i>Am_Ac_Tm_Tt_Tv</i>	-	3	3	6
20	<i>Tm_Tt</i>	-	5	1	6
21	<i>Eo_Tm</i>	-	4	1	5
22	<i>Eo_Tm_Tv_Bb</i>	-	5	-	5
23	<i>Am_Ac_Tm</i>	1	2	1	4
24	<i>Am_Tm_Tt_Tv_Bb</i>	1	3	-	4
25	<i>Am_Ac_Tm_Tv</i>	-	-	3	3
26	<i>Am_AspO_Tm_Tt_Tv_Bbov</i>	-	1	2	3
27	<i>AspO_Bb</i>	-	2	1	3
28	<i>AspO_Tm_Tt</i>	-	2	1	3
29	<i>AspO_Tm_Tt_Tv_Bb</i>	-	-	3	3
30	<i>AspO_Tm_Tt_Tv_Bbov</i>	-	1	2	3
31	<i>R_Tm_Tv</i>	-	2	1	3
32	<i>Tm_Tt_Bb</i>	-	2	1	3

33	<i>Tm_Tv_Bb</i>	1	1	1	3
34	<i>Ap_Tm</i>	-	1	1	2
35	<i>Ap_Tm_Tt</i>	-	-	2	2
36	<i>Ap_Tm_Tt_Tv_Bb</i>	-	-	2	2
37	<i>Ac_AspO</i>	-	-	2	2
38	<i>Am_Bb</i>	2	-	-	2
39	<i>Am_Ac_AspO_Tm</i>	-	-	2	2
40	<i>Am_Ac_Er_Tm_Tt_Tv</i>	-	-	2	2
41	<i>Am_Tm_Tt_Tv_Bbov</i>	-	1	1	2
42	<i>Am_Eo_Tm_Bbov</i>	1	-	1	2
43	<i>Am_Ac_AspO_Tm_Tv</i>	-	-	2	2
44	<i>Am_AspO_Tm_Tt</i>	-	2	-	2
45	<i>Am_AspO_Tm_Tt_Bb</i>	-	1	1	2
46	<i>Am_Ac_Er_AspO_Tm_Tv</i>	-	1	1	2
47	<i>Am_R_Tm</i>	-	2	-	2
48	<i>Ac_Tm_Tt_Tv</i>	-	2	-	2
49	<i>AspO_R_Tm_Tv</i>	-	-	2	2
50	<i>Tm_Bb</i>	1	-	1	2
51	<i>Tm_Tt_Tv_Bbov</i>	-	-	2	2
52	<i>Ap_Tm_Tt_Bb</i>	-	1	-	1
53	<i>Ap_Tm_Tv_Bb</i>	-	-	1	1
54	<i>Am_Ac_AspO_Tv</i>	1	-	-	1
55	<i>Am_Ac_AspO_Bb</i>	1	-	-	1
56	<i>Am_Ac_Er_AspO</i>	-	1	-	1
57	<i>Am_Ac_Tm_Bb</i>	1	-	-	1
58	<i>Am_Tm_Tt</i>	-	-	1	1
59	<i>Am_Tm_Tt_Bb</i>	1	-	-	1
60	<i>Am_Tm_Tv_Bb</i>	-	-	1	1
61	<i>Am_AspO_Tv</i>	-	1	-	1
62	<i>Am_Ac_AspO_Tm_Tt_Tv_Bbov</i>	-	-	1	1
63	<i>Am_Ac_AspO_R_Tm</i>	-	-	1	1
64	<i>Am_AspO_TM_TV_Bbov</i>	-	1	-	1
65	<i>Am_Ac_AspO_Tm_Tv_Bb</i>	-	1	-	1
66	<i>Am_AspO_R_Tm_Tv</i>	-	-	1	1
67	<i>Am_R_Tm_Tv</i>	-	-	1	1
68	<i>Am_R_Tm_Tt_Tv</i>	-	-	1	1
69	<i>Ac_Tm_Tt_Tv_Bb</i>	1	-	-	1
70	<i>AspO_R</i>	-	-	1	1
71	<i>AspO_Tv_Bb</i>	1	-	-	1
72	<i>AspO_Tm_Tt_Bb</i>	-	1	-	1
73	<i>Er_Tm</i>	-	-	1	1
74	<i>Er_Tm_Tt_Tv</i>	-	-	1	1
75	<i>Er_Tm_Tv</i>	-	-	1	1
76	<i>R_Tm_Tt_Tv</i>	-	-	1	1
77	<i>Tv_Bb</i>	-	1	-	1